

OPTIMIZATION OF FIBER ORIENTATION FOR LAMINATED CIRCULAR CYLINDRICAL SHELLS UNDER UNIFORM LOAD

Shaher A. Kassaimah^{*}, Abdel-Aziz M. Mohamed Ph.D.^{**}, Faysal A. Kolkailah, Ph.D., P.E.^{*}

^{*} Aeronautical Engineering Department, California polytechnic State University

San Luis Obispo, CA. 93407

^{**} Department of Management Science, California State University-Northridge
Northridge, CA. 91330

ABSTRACT

In this paper, optimum fiber orientations for simply supported laminated shells under uniformly distributed load are determined. Angle-ply laminates with orthotropic laminae are considered. The problem is formulated as an unconstrained non-linear programming problem. The objective function of the model is to minimize the deflection. The complex search algorithm is employed to solve the single objective optimization problem. Optimum fiber orientations and the corresponding deflection are presented for glass/epoxy, carbon/epoxy and boron/epoxy composite materials at levels of aspect ratios. Optimization results reveal that the shells made out of carbon/epoxy have the lowest deflection and the ones made out of glass/epoxy have the highest deflection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, filamentary composite materials have been suggested for the primary structure of aircraft and spacecraft. The reason is primarily the weight savings that can be attained. One of the design criterion that must be considered in the design of composite is the uniformly distributed lateral load. Several theoretical and experimental studies have been published on the laminated composite plates and shells [1-5]. Optimal design for simply supported circular cylindrical laminated shells of composite material subjected to axial compression and lateral vibration loading is considered [2,4]. The design problem as formulated in most of those studies was to determine the optimal fiber orientations for a ant-symmetric angle-ply laminate. The optimal design for simply supported circular cylindrical laminated shells under lateral vibration is considered in [4]. The criterion considered in the studies [2,4] is to maximize the reduced critical buckling stress and natural frequency. The objective in reference [1,3] is to determine the fiber orientations for anti-symmetric angle-ply laminated graphite/epoxy plates under uniformly distributed load.

In this paper, fiber orientations corresponding to the optimum objective function values for antisymmetric angle-ply simply supported laminated circular cylindrical shells of boron/epoxy, carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy composite materials with orthotropic layers under uniformly distributed lateral load are determined. The design criterion are the to minimize the deflection. Each layer in each shell is assumed to have the same thickness and an equal numbers of fibers. Inhomogeneity in the directions of each shell (stacking sequence) is taken into account in the calculation; therefore, the present study allows almost complete freedom for the choice of all the ply angles.

2. OPTIMIZATION MODEL DEVELOPMENT

In this study, optimal design model for simply supported laminated circular cylindrical shells of composite materials subject to uniform lateral load is considered. The problem is to determine the optimal directions of all layers corresponding to the deflection. Material properties, the thickness of each layer in each shell, the number of layers, the aspect ratio of the shells have preassigned values. We consider a simply supported shell with length l , load ratio k in the x direction, radius r and thickness t in the z direction is considered. The shell is under lateral load composed of six orthotropic layer, fibers of which are oriented alternatively at angles $+\alpha$ and $-\alpha$. The material properties and the layer thicknesses are symmetrical to the middle surface. Plates with these characteristics are commonly known as anti-symmetric angle ply laminated construction.

The equilibrium equations for general laminated plates were derived by Whitney and Leissa [5]. Those equations were simplified for the case of angle-ply shells under lateral load. The relationship between the deflection $\phi(\underline{\alpha}, m, n)$, the fiber orientations $\underline{\alpha}$ and the half-wave in the x and y directions m and n , respectively is determined. This relationship can be stated as:

$$\phi(\underline{\alpha}, m, n) = \frac{T_{11}(T_{12}^2 - T_{11}T_{22})}{mn\{(T_{12}^2 - T_{11}T_{22})(T_{11}T_{33} - T_{12}^2) + (T_{12}T_{13} - T_{11}T_{23})^2\}} \quad (1)$$

where

$$T_{11} = -(A_{11}\bar{m}^2 + A_{66}\bar{n}^2) \quad (2)$$

$$T_{12} = (A_{12} + A_{66})\bar{m}\bar{n} \quad (3)$$

$$T_{13} = \frac{1}{r}A_{12}\bar{m} + B_{11}\bar{m}^3 + (B_{12} + 2B_{66})\bar{m}\bar{n}^2 \quad (4)$$

$$T_{22} = -(A_{66}\bar{m}^2 + A_{22}\bar{n}^2) \quad (5)$$

$$T_{23} = -\frac{1}{r}(A_{22}\bar{n} + B_{22}\bar{n}^3 + (B_{12} + 2B_{66})\bar{m}^2\bar{n}) \quad (6)$$

$$T_{33} = -\left(\frac{2}{r}B_{12}\bar{m}^2 + \frac{2}{r}B_{22}\bar{n}^2 + \frac{1}{r^2}A_{22} + D_{11}\bar{m}^4\right) - (2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})\bar{m}\bar{n}^3) - D_{22}\bar{n}^4 \quad (7)$$

In which

$$\bar{m} = \frac{m\pi}{l} \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{n} = \frac{n}{r} \quad (9)$$

Where A_{ij} , B_{ij} , D_{ij} are the extensional, coupling and bending stiffness, respectively. The objective of the design problem is to minimize the deflection, $\phi(\underline{\alpha}, m, n)$. The values of the constants m and n shown in the previous formula are determined from the following minimization problem when $\underline{\alpha} = 0$:

$$\Phi(\underline{\alpha}) = \min \phi(\alpha, m, n) \quad (10)$$

Once the optimal values of m and n are determined, the deflection is determined as

$$\text{Maximize } \Phi(\underline{\alpha}) \quad (11)$$

The design variables considered in this optimization model are $\underline{\alpha} = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_6)$, where α_i is the angle of the i^{th} fiber orientation. Since the optimization model is so complicated, the complex search algorithm [6] is employed to solve the optimization problem. The optimization problem is an unconstrained nonlinear programming problem. The complex search algorithm is a search method that does not require the derivative of the model objective function or constraint. It does require a starting feasible solution. The algorithm generates $N + 1$ random feasible points, where N is the number of randomly generated values for the design variables $\underline{\alpha}$. Then, the algorithm evaluates the objective function value at each point and the point corresponding to the lowest objective function value is rejected. A new feasible point is generated by reflecting the rejected point a certain distance through the centroid of the remaining points. Thus, if x^R is the rejected point and x^C is the centroid of the remaining points, the new point x^N is calculated as:

$$X^N = X^C + \alpha(X^C - X^R) \quad (12)$$

where α is recommended to be equal to 1.3. The search is terminated when they are sufficiently close together or when the differences between the function values evaluated at the points become small enough.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optimization of fiber orientation for simply supported laminated circular cylindrical shells under uniform distributed lateral load is illustrated in this paper by considering six laminates. The thickness of each layer is assumed to be 0.01 inch. The number of half-waves in the x and y directions is varied from 1 to 10 and from 1 to 5 respectively. Three composite materials are considered in this study: Glass/Epoxy (GFRP), Boron/Epoxy (BFRP) and Carbon/Epoxy (CFRP)

Table 1 Optimum Fiber Directions

A. Ratio	Optimum Fiber Orientation (deg.)						Deflection		
R/L	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5	α_6	ϕ_{GFRP}	ϕ_{BFRP}	ϕ_{CFRP}
0.2	86.8	80.8	87.8	87.9	87.9	89.8	18.23		
	85.0	85.8	86.4	86.5	86.7	86.6		8.21	
	83.5	83.4	83.5	86.5	85.6	89.9			3.79
0.4	70.3	71.4	72.0	72.9	72.7	73.6	7.3		
	70.1	70.4	70.8	71.5	71.6	72.3		3.52	
	67.6	69.3	71.1	71.5	71.0	71.6			1.53
0.6	66.3	75.3	80.6	84.8	76.5	81.5	4.5		
	60.8	66.9	67.5	65.4	65.3	59.9		1.60	
	58.9	57.0	54.0	66.0	56.9	57.0			0.84
0.8	76.9	78.9	70.9	78.4	75.0	76.0	6.9		
	75.8	74.9	75.0	73.9	78.9	75.0		3.20	
	74.9	72.0	72.4	73.1	73.4	74.9			1.44
1.0	61.3	67.5	77.5	76.4	77.4	77.0	10.23		
	60.7	63.1	62.1	63.7	62.1	62.3		4.52	
	58.9	57.9	56.3	56.3	56.8	54.9			2.13

Figure 1. Deflection, ϕ , versus plate aspect ratio R/L

composite materials. The major Young's modulus (E_L), the minor Young's modulus (E_T), the major poisson's (ν_{LT}), and the shear modulus (G_{LT}) are presented as follows:

$$(GFRP)E_L = 7.8 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2, E_T = 2.6 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2, \nu_{LT} = 0.25, G_{LT} = 1.3 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2$$

$$(BFRP)E_L = 30.0 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2, E_T = 3.0 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2, \nu_{LT} = 0.30, G_{LT} = 1.0 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2$$

$$(CFRP)E_L = 30.0 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2, E_T = 0.75 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2, \nu_{LT} = 0.25, G_{LT} = 0.375 \times 10^6 \text{ lb/in}^2$$

Five levels of aspect ratios ($R/L = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ and 1) are considered in this study. The optimization results of the complex search algorithm are tabulated in Table 1, in this table, the optimal fiber orientations and the corresponding deflection are presented for six-layered circular cylindrical shells made out of boron/epoxy, carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy composite materials. The shells are assumed to be under uniformly distributed lateral load. Results presented in this table reveal that the optimal fiber orientations are so close for the three composite materials at the same aspect ratio. Fig. 1 shows that the shells made out of carbon/epoxy composite materials have the lowest deflection and the shells made out of glass/epoxy have the highest deflection.

4. CONCLUSION

Optimal fiber orientations are determined for simply supported antisymmetric, angle-ply laminates circular cylindrical shells under uniformly distributed load. Numerical results show that the deflection decreases as the aspect ratio reaches, ($R/L = 0.6$), after this point the deflection starts increasing. Also, it has been found that the laminated shells made out of carbon/epoxy composite material has the lowest deflection and the shells made out of glass/epoxy composite material has the highest deflection. When similar shells are subjected to axial compression or lateral vibration instead of uniformly distributed load [2,4] respectively, the laminated shells made out of carbon/epoxy composite material will have the highest reduced critical buckling stress and the highest natural frequency.

5. REFERENCES

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